

A REVIEW ON FRUIT SEGREGATION USING DEEPLARNING

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ABSTRACT

Automation, as a fundamental property in the agricultural sector, raises and improves the standard and expands the efficiency of manufacturing goods. The improved sorting of goods had an impact on the quality evaluation. Higher output was needed as technology advanced to meet human needs and industry demands. Fruits Segregation using Deep Learning uses image processing to detect and differentiate between various types of fruits. This paper proposes an OpenCV, Python and Convolution Neural Network (CNN) to complete the segregation of three major fruits: apple, orange, and banana. Also, this paper discusses literature reviews of various related works on this topic. This paper presents a comparison of different methods proposed by researchers for classifying fruits.

Keywords: Deep Learning, Image Processing, CNN, Sequential Model, Computer Vision.

I. Introduction

70% of India's population relies on agriculture. Agriculture is extremely beneficial to the expansion of the economy by providing food and raw materials to non-agricultural sectors. Agriculture needs a lot of manpower. Farmers must devote a significant amount of time to manual sorting and examining fruits from harvest through the growth period. Manual sorting does not always produce satisfactory results, so efficient farming techniques are required. Used to get better yield and growth with less human effort. A lot of recent research has been done on the computer's ability to reduce processing time and provide precise results. Digital image processing as a computer-based technique has been widely used in agriculture for segregation purposes. Image processing is a type of signal processing where an image is given as an input, such as photographs or frames of video, and the output obtained will be image parameters or an image. Also, India's population is rapidly increasing. The quantity of food has been the most affected by population growth. As the population grows, so does the demand for high-quality food. In this proposal, we have been discussing fruit segregation. For the development of accurate and fast segregation of fruit, the grading process takes place. It is done based on the overall quality features of the fruit, like shape, colour, and size. Recent developments in automatic vision-based technology. Use of this technology is increasing in agriculture and the fruit industry. An automatic

fruit segregation system will be used for the sorting and grading of various fruits.

II. Literature Review

Dhameshwari Sahu and Ravindra M. P. (2017) [1] use computer vision applications and image processing for identification and consistency assessment in agriculture applications. Fruit defect detection and identification is a challenging task to accomplish at near-human levels of detection. The authors create a structure that is beneficial to the seller and can be used to apply computer vision to the automated separation of fruits from various types of fruits. Using digital image processing, the authors created a method to detect defects and determine the ripeness of fruits based on their size and shape.

Bhargava and Bansal (2018) [2] conducted their most recent research on fruit and vegetable quality assessments using a monitoring process that includes pre-processing, categorization, and fruit and vegetable extraction based on various compositions and classifications. The paper also commented on a comparison of various ideas presented by analysts for quality assurance, including ultrasound, infrared imaging, and tomographic imaging. The test result was drawn to infer that the ideas proposed could be used as a separate colour space to extract the colour feature and that the system generated by them is free of bias.

Aaron Don M. Africa, Anna Rovia V. Tabala, and Mharela Angela A. Tan (2020) [3] concluded in their journal that, prior to their release in the market, ripe fruits are classified

and graded for quality by humans. Recent studies, however, indicate that using physical characteristics like shape, colour, and texture as the only criteria for estimating quality could be prone to human error since these factors require consistency during the examination. Several studies have proposed and presented different methods to detect and classify fruits more accurately. The authors were able to enumerate some of the most widely used and most effective methods, including deep learning, image illumination, faster-CNN, and the use of a gas chromatograph for the detection of ethylene gas.

Anand Upadhyay, Sunny Singh and Shona Kanojia in 2020 & 2023 [4][5] use Convolution Neural Network Based Segregation of Ripe and Raw Bananas. The paper commented that this technique reduces the efforts of humans and can give up to 90% accuracy. This study used a convolutional neural network (CNN) to classify bananas as raw or ripe without the use of human labor. Bananas were classified by their colour appearance in the CNN classification and not only this, but it can also be used to classify numerous other types of fruits and vegetables.

Venkat Ghodke, Suresh Pungaiyah, Mohamed Shamout, Allwyn Sundarraj, Maidul Islam Judder and S. Vijaprasath (2022) [6] developed a system for quality rating and product classification to eliminate the wastage of fruits due to the transportation of overripe or already rotten fruits during the logistics. Firstly, start the process by including the image dataset, and the first step is preprocessing. The next step is segmenting the images from the stage of pre-processing filtered images, which helps resolve the images. Extracting the features based on the image weights and evaluating them for classification. Also using the training and testing images for classification, it includes separating or relating color, texture, shape, and faults. Finally, classification using the LSVR process improves image quality and assists the industry in separating products. The use of images in the automated packaging process improves the quality of the results in more ways than ever before.

Nagnath Aherwadi and Usha Mittal (2022) [7], published a paper. The paper shows well-known techniques of image processing,

machine learning, and deep learning technologies that can be used in the maturity classification, quality identification, and shelf-life identification of fruit. Different algorithms and techniques used for all the above problems are discussed in that paper. First Fruit is identified, and further maturity classification is performed based on fruit maturity status in order to determine the quality and shelf life of fruits.

Norhidayah Mohd Rozi and colleagues (2021) [8] investigated the Development of Fruits Artificial Intelligence Segregation. Using a hardware-based system and artificial intelligence, they showed how fruits can be segregated without the need for human involvement. To separate the fruits, the system used a Raspberry Pi and a camera. Their system's accuracy was up to 97%. Their system can apply the liveness discovery techniques to the fruit segregation system using software, in which the sorting discovery is performed by the shape and colour of the fruit.

Goutam Kambale and Dr. Nitin Bigli (2017) [9] conducted their survey on Crop Disease Identification and Classification Using Pattern Recognition and Digital Image Processing Techniques. Their system requires a high quality image to be captured using a digital camera, processing that image using image processing software, and then identifying or classifying the disease using pattern recognition methodology to help farmers recognise the disease more accurately, which cannot be done with our naked eyes.

Aafreen Kazi and Siba Prasad Panda (2022) [10] did research on determining the freshness of fruits in the food industry by image classification. Their system was developed based on transfer learning methodologies. Rather than enforcing the traditional CNN architecture, their system attempts to investigate the capability of transfer learning with respect to CNN models in image classification of fruits. Based on their test scores, the system attempted to evaluate the best performing model on image data consisting of six different types of fruits. The results suggest that the freshness of fruits could be determined with high accurateness by using traditional and residual convolutional neural networks.

III. Methodology

Software Tools

The CCN techniques applied in this work use several two main software: Python 3.8 and OpenCV.

Python 3.8

Python is a flexible language for programming that is easy to understand. These have successful high-level knowledge structures and a simple but efficient approach to object-oriented programming. For all major platforms from the Python Web site, a python interpreter and the full standard library are freely available and can be freely distributed in source or binary form. The same section also provides distributions and pointers to some free Python third-party modules, programs and tools, and additional documentation.

OpenCV

The Open-Source Computer Vision Library (OpenCV) is an open-source computer vision and machine learning software library. Over 2500 optimized algorithms in the library include a broad set of computer vision and machine learning algorithms, both classic and state-of-the-art. These algorithms can be used to identify and recognize faces, identify objects, classify human activity in videos, monitor camera movements, track moving objects, extract 3D object models, generate 3D point clouds from stereo cameras, stitch images together to create a high-resolution image of the entire scene, check for an identical image from an image database, and delete red eyes from a flash image.

Convolution Neural Network

Deep learning algorithm used for image classification was CNN. CNN is composed of several convolutional, pooling layer and a general neural network layer which is called as a fully connected layer, shows a good performance for the input data of 2-dimension structure such as image. Convolutional layer makes it possible to extract features without being affected by the size or position of the target on the input image through the convolution operation. Pooling layer reduces the feature through the subsampling in the process to reduce the data increased by the convolutional progress. The convolutional and pooling operation is being repeated, and the feature extraction performance is determined according to this. As the features are obtained through convolutional and pooling layers, the classification task is performed in the final full connected layer (LeCun et al., 2010). It was used for the GPU possible parallel processing utilizing GPGPU (General-Purpose computing on Graphics Processing Units) concept to train fast, because CNN algorithm requires a lot of computation.

IV. Conclusion

In this paper, A review on Fruit Segregation Using Deep Learning, Deep learning algorithms best techniques for fruit detection, maturity classification and quality assessment depend on the datasets used for that experiment. [5] CNN model achieved 79.49% accuracy whereas SVM achieved 69% accuracy, so in this case, the Deep learning technique is best. [20] Again here CNN got the highest accuracy 91.6% as compared to an image processing technique accuracy of 60%. So, the working accuracy totally depends on the dataset and techniques used for detection and classification with quality assessment of fruits.

V. Future Research

It is recommended to do more research on this paper and determine what can be improved. In the future, we can implement this software-based system on a larger scale by adding it to the mega factories, which require the segregation of fruits and quality to be maintained for their raw products, such as fruits. We can do more than just fruit segregation if the perfect set of datasets is made available, or

we can build a perfect set of data by capturing high-quality images. In the near future, we can also implement our software with a robotic arm to remove unripe or overripe fruit from conveyor belts used in the packaging industry, which will eliminate the need for humans to manually remove it before it reaches the final packaging point.

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